

Investigate the Effects of Lockdowns on COVID-19 Cases

Data Collection

What data will you collect or create?

This experiment includes two datasets:

1. Entwicklung der täglich neu gemeldeten Fallzahl des Coronavirus (COVID-19) in Österreich seit 25. Februar 2020 (status as of 14th April 2021) downloaded from the webpage <https://de.statista.com/> with the statistic-id: 1150777 (Accessed on 14 April 2021). URL: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/1150777/umfrage/entwicklung-der-taeglichen-fallzahl-des-coronavirus-in-oesterreich/>. The format of this dataset is an excel file (volume: 18,4kB) and it includes just two columns (the dates and the regarding numbers of COVID-19 cases). The time series goes from the 26th February 2020 until the 13th April 2021. I'm not able to share this data, because it's not allowed for people without a Corporate- or Enterprise-Account on <https://de.statista.com/>.
2. COVID-19: Google Mobility TrendsCOVID-19: Google Mobility Trends (status as of 14th April 2021) downloaded from the webpage <https://ourworldindata.org/covid-google-mobility-trends> (Accessed on 14 April 2021). The format of this dataset is an csv-file (3,5MB) and it includes how the daily number of visitors (or time spent in percent) in categorized places has changed compared to baseline days (the median value for the 5-week period from January 3 to February 6, 2020) for several countries. Furthermore it includes the following columns: Entity, Code, Day, retail_and_recreation, grocery_and_pharmacy, residential, transit_stations, parks, workplaces. The time series goes from the 17th February 2020 until the 11th April 2021. The data was pulished by Google LLC "Google COVID-19 Community Mobility Reports" (URL: <https://www.google.com/covid19/mobility/>). For downloading and using this dataset, you have to accept the terms of use of Goggle: <https://policies.google.com/terms?hl=de>.

How will the data be collected or created?

1. Entwicklung der täglich neu gemeldeten Fallzahl des Coronavirus (COVID-19) in Österreich seit 25. Februar 2020:
 - **source:** BMSGPK (Österreich)
 - **levied by:** BMSGPK (Österreich)
 - **published by:** AGES
2. COVID-19: Google Mobility TrendsCOVID-19: Google provide an overview of what its mobility trends represent and how it's measured here: https://support.google.com/covid19-mobility/answer/9824897?hl=en&ref_topic=9822927

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

On Github, I created the repository 'digitalpreservation-dmp' (URL: <https://github.com/MyStudentAcct/digitalpreservation-dmp/blob/main/README.md>). The documentation is captured in the pdf file `documentation.pdf` (`/documentation/documentation.pdf`). The metadata file can be found inside the project folder (`/documentation/metadata.xml`). Additionally a descriptive file is added, which explains the axes and units used in the output files, this files can be found inside the project folder as well (`/documentation/description.txt`).

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

There are no ethical issues. Because for the datasource 'COVID-19: Google Mobility TrendsCOVID-19', Google used leading anonymization technology, in order to keep users activity data private and secure. This includes differential privacy, a process in which "artificial noise" is applied to this dataset. In this way, Google can generate statistics and at the same time prevent individual persons from being identified.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

As I already mentioned, I'm not able to share the dataset 'Entwicklung der täglich neu gemeldeten Fallzahl des Coronavirus (COVID-19) in Österreich seit 25. Februar 2020', because it's not allowed for people without a Corporate- or Enterprise-Account on <https://de.statista.com/>.

But in order to get this datasoure, please follow these instructions:

1. Go to <https://de.statista.com/> an create a free basic account.
2. Use the URL <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/1150777/umfrage/entwicklung-der-taeglichen-fallzahl-des-coronavirus-in-oesterreich/> or the statistic-D 1150777 to find the regarding dataset (status as of 14th April 2021; it's irrelevant if there is a newer version with a longer time series available, because if you run the code, it will be cut, in order to replicate the results in the documentation).
3. Download the dataset as an excel file into the folder `raw_data` and rename it to `'statistic_id1150777.xlsx'`

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

For running the experiment, I stored the data on my local disk. Furthermore, I did a backup of the data on my TUownCloud.

How will you manage access and security?

Because the data is not confidential there are no special security measures necessary.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

The data source 'COVID-19: Google Mobility TrendsCOVID-19: Google Mobility Trends' is just available for a limited time - as long as they are helping health officials contain the spread of COVID-19.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

I stored the data source 'COVID-19: Google Mobility TrendsCOVID-19: Google Mobility Trends' in my the repository folder (raw_data/changes-visitors-covid.csv) on Github (URL: <https://github.com/MyStudentAcct/digitalpreservation-dmp/blob/main/README.md>).

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

I will share the data source 'COVID-19: Google Mobility TrendsCOVID-19: Google Mobility Trends' via Github (URL: <https://github.com/MyStudentAcct/digitalpreservation-dmp/blob/main/README.md>).

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

As already mentioned, I'm not able to share the dataset 'Entwicklung der täglich neu gemeldeten Fallzahl des Coronavirus (COVID-19) in Österreich seit 25. Februar 2020', because it's not allowed for people without a Corporate- or Enterprise-Account on <https://de.statista.com/>. But in my repository is a description, in order to download this data source.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

Because I'm the only person, who is responsible for this project, I guess it's me.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

Read the README.md or README.pdf file in my repository.